

CHIST-ERA-19

SEEDS Project

D2.1. ENBIOS as MuSIASEM checker. Software companion documentation

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1 ENBIOS description

ENBIOS (Environmental and Bioeconomic System Analysis) is an framework for the assessment of environmental impacts and resource requirements of energy system pathways according to policy scenarios (Madrid-López, Süsser, et al., 2021; Madrid-López, Talens-Peiró, et al., 2021). It integrates the bottom-up capabilities of life cycle assessment (LCA) and the three sustainability checks of the Multi-scale Integrated Assessment of Socio-Ecosystem Metabolism (MuSIASEM) (Giampietro & Mayumi, 2000a, 2000b).

ENBIOS was first implemented as a software as part of the Horizon 2020 project SENTINEL (Nebot Medina et al., 2021) and later updated as a standalone python package (Soleymani et al., 2023) in the LIVEN project. This second version uses the Brightway2 (Mutel, 2017) LCA python package for calculations.

ENBIOS requires an energy system scenario, usually taken from **configurations** calculated by energy system optimization models (ESOMs). These configurations detail energy supply, demand, and transfer information for a number of technologies. Technologies are represented as **activities**, which can be later aggregated at different levels according to different attributes, depending on the study objectives. Users must also have access to **life cycle inventory data** compatible with Brightway2. This data can be self-developed or taken from databases, like Ecoinvent.

In SEEDS, we have coupled ENBIOS with an ESOM for Portugal (Lombardi, 2022) based on the Calliope framework (Pfenninger & Pickering, 2018) and the SPORES approach. The SPORES approach does not return a single solution of the energy system, but an option space of near-optimal solutions, which in our case is formed by 261 energy system configurations.

The outcome of ENBIOS is a detailed analysis of environmental impacts and resource demands, delineated by activity across the system's hierarchical aggregation for each of the 261 energy configurations.

The development of different sections of ENBIOS is done in different projects. In the SEEDS project, the works have focused on the further development of the dendrogram definition, changes in the calculations to allow multi-level impacts assessments and in proposing a workflow to better integrate LCA data within MuSIASEM.

2 Avoiding double accounting in environmental assessment: The SPARKS workflow

SPARKS (de Tomás-Pascual, 2023) is a Brightway2 workflow designed to generate enbios-compatible inputs using Calliope results. This code is tailored to generate data for a wide range of scenarios and includes functions to address common issues in LCA of energy systems, such as double accounting. Additionally, it provides high flexibility in converting and adapting different units to match Calliope and LCA data. Altogether, it is possible to generate this new information by simply processing the outputs from Calliope and an Excel "mother" file containing the basic information.

Figure 1. Structure of Sparks

3 Definition of new dendrograms and activity categories

In MuSIASEM, the grouping of activities in a hierarchical organization is called a dendrogram. Each of these groupings answers to one energy system scenario in ENBIOS. In SEEDS, ENBIOS was coupled with the SPORES model for Portugal, developing the idea of **option-space dendrograms** that will allow us to compare all 261 configurations with the same system structuring. An example is shown in figure 1.

Figure 2. Example of an option-space dendrogram representation in SEEDS.

Following the MuSIASEM semantics, in the dendrogram, each of the nodes is considered a processor. The lowest level of the hierarchy shows structural processors, which are tangible, susceptible to have a location and a timing. The rest of the nodes are considered functions related to energy supply and use (in level n+1).

4 MuSIASEM accounting workflow

LCA and MuSIASEM have two different accounting semantics that are shown in figure 3. Whereas life cycle follows a pathway that includes all production stages related to the production of one unit of energy regardless of when these happen, MuSIASEM follows a *snapshot* of the energy system configuration, generally related to a given year. In LCA's sequential pathway, all the impacts associated with the value chain of a technology are associated with the productive activity of that technology. The MuSIASEM accounting considers only direct impacts.

Figure 3. The two accounting schemes integrated in ENBIOS

The MuSIASEM accounting procedure in ENBIOS considers the energy system as both an energy carrier supplier and end user. It starts by taking a close look at each technology's electricity production and use. This is done by comparing the technology's specific energy use profile with the amount of energy it produces. Next, the procedure organizes energy use data. It breaks down the construction and operation phases into smaller steps, which helps to understand where and when energy is used. This is important because it allows for a detailed analysis of energy use over time and across different locations.

The hierarchical aggregation proposed in the dendrogram adds up all the energy use data from the smaller steps to calculate the energy used by the entire energy sector against the energy used by the societal system, allowing for the estimations of trade-offs between the impacts that are produced and saved.

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